

***D1.2: Food loss and waste
economic model development & SILL-
based validation***

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1: Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
CES	Constant Elasticity of Substitution
EC	European Commission
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HRI	Hotels, Restaurants and Institutions
JRC	Joint Research Center
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Lab
THS	Transport, Handling and Storage
WP	Work Package
WRAP	Waste & Resources Action Programme

Executive summary

This deliverable presents a theoretical partial equilibrium food supply chain model that will later be used in Deliverable 1.3 to analyze various policy and technological options to curb food loss and waste for selected commodities. We consider six stages of the supply chain: the farmer; transportation, handling, and storage (THS); the processor; retail; hotels, restaurants, and institutions (HRI); and the final consumer with her consumption of food at home and away from home. We distinguish between pre-harvest and post-harvest losses at the farm level. We also distinguish between food purchases and consumption at the consumer level. At each stage of the supply chain, we model two distinct channels through which a supply chain agent can change her food loss and waste abatement cost: the scale effect due to the change in the quantity of food produced (purchased) and the effect of changing the rate of edible food loss and waste. The food loss and waste abatement cost function is an entry point to model alternative policy interventions or new SILL-based technological solutions to curb food loss and waste along a selected food supply chain.

1. Project introduction

1.1. ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2: ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 work packages (WPs) with different goals, tasks, and deliverables. The objectives of WP1 are (1) to outline a conceptual framework for measuring the economic effects of food loss and waste (FLW) along the food chain; (2) to develop a high-level economic model encompassing the food supply chain actors and validate it by the SILLs; (3) to quantitatively assess various FLW interventions by running simulations with the FLW model. The objective of task 1.1 was achieved by deliverable 1.1. This deliverable, D1.2, will fulfill the objective of task 1.2 of WP1. We will present an economic FLW model that covers the most important stages of the supply chain. This deliverable also explains how the interventions of SILLs can be modeled. The model we present in this deliverable will be used for the simulations that contribute to fulfilling task 1.3.

Figure 3: WP1 tasks, deliverables, objectives.

1.2. Mapping ZeroW output

This chapter aims to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal deliverable and task description, against the current document.

Table 2: Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW Component Title	GA	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE				
D1.2 FLW economic model		FLW economic model – Will deliver a SILL-validated model	Chapters 5	Chapter 5 provides a discussion on how the SILLs results will be modeled.
TASKS				
T1.2 FLW economic model development & SILL-based validation		The model will analyze the economic effects of interventions, both public and private, on FLW affecting the vertical food supply chain and the markets for valorizing/disposing of FLW. It will consider consumers, processors/intermediaries, and producers, allowing each to choose their inputs, product output, and the amount of waste optimally, allowing markets at each	Chapters 3, 4, 5	Chapter 3 presents the notion of food loss and waste abatement cost function, and chapter 4 explains the modules of the supply chain stages and how they are linked. Chapter 5 provides an entry point to implement the SILLs’ interventions into our

	<p>stage of the food supply chain to equilibrate. Such a model would allow for examining targeted policies' expected and unexpected effects on other parts of the system. We will proceed in two steps. First, we will present a model for each actor individually. This will allow us to identify the unique effects an actor has on the rest of the supply chain. Second, we will link all stages of the supply chain to learn about possible interaction effects among them. We will use our consultations with SILLs to calibrate and validate the results of the numerical model in Task 1.3.</p>		<p>model and then quantitatively examine their effects.</p>
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1.3. Deliverable overview

This report presents the structure and functioning of an economic partial equilibrium model that shows the effects of FLW reduction along different stages of the supply chain. The model can determine the effects of an FLW reduction at a specific stage in the supply chain and the cascading effects on other stages. The outcomes of deliverable **D1.1** (FLW conceptual model) are included in this report to explain how the FLW-reducing developments of the **WP4** SILLs will be modeled in **D1.3**. The model can simulate FLW reduction proposals of SILLs at the commodity level. The empirical simulations of this model will be executed in **T1.3** and can provide more detailed insights compared to the Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model that will also be used in **T1.3**. The CGE model will shed light on cross-sectoral effects in the economy, which we are unable to do with our model.

This deliverable links to **T5.2** that will assess the impacts of the SILLs. Furthermore, D1.2 is indirectly (through the outcomes of the empirical simulations of **D1.3**) linked to **T8.2**, which will develop 'just' transition pathways to a near-zero FLW society by 2050. The model presented in this deliverable can show which stages of the supply chain are expected to benefit from FLW reduction and which stages are expected to lose.

2. Structure of the supply chain

The model presented in this deliverable builds on and extends the food supply chain model developed by de Gorter et al. (2021), for the World Bank report presented in Sethi (2020). The main extension includes the pre-harvest food loss part of the model and the inclusion of uncertainty in the decision making of the representative farmer. Our consumer module builds on the model of Hamilton and Richards (2019) and Drabik, de Gorter, and Reynolds (2019) but we use a different functional form of the food waste abatement cost function. Specifically, we place a natural bound on the maximum achievable rate of edible food waste rate and explicitly model the (exogenous) rate of inedible food loss and waste. An important novelty with respect to the previous models is the consideration of the scale effect in reducing the food loss and waste abatement cost at each stage of the supply chain; that is, the agents in our supply chain do not only choose an optimal rate of edible food loss and waste (i.e., the rate is endogenous) but also the optimal quantity of food produced (purchased).

We consider six stages of the supply chain, from producer to consumer, where the final consumption is split into consumption at home and away from home. Food is produced by the representative farmer; both pre- and post-harvest losses are considered. The pre-harvest losses are the result of uncertain factors such as weather, pests, or market prices. After harvest, food losses still occur due, for example, to bad storage conditions. The remaining share of the produced goods is modeled to be sold to the transportation, handling, and storage (THS) sector that sells the product to the processor. The processor can either sell the food to the retailer or the food service sector (hotels, restaurants, and institutions). The food that is sold to the retailer ends up with the final consumer at home, while the food that is sold by the processor to the food service sector is consumed by the final consumer away from home. Figure 4 provides a graphical representation of the food supply chain in the model.

*Food served at hotels, restaurants and institutions (like universities, hospitals etc.)

Figure 4: Stages of a food supply chain in our model (based on de Gorter et al., 2021)

Each stage of the supply chain generates an amount of FLW; in our model, FLW can end up at four destinations: landfill (or incineration), donations, recycling, and upcycling (i.e., a possible use of FLW for the production of a new product of higher quality or value). The model allows us to determine the allocation of FWL across the four destinations at the level of the supply chain but not at individual stages. Net trade in a modeled commodity is included at the level of THS, processor, and retail.

3. Modeling food loss and waste abatement

Agents in the food supply chain choose optimal purchases of inputs for further production (consumption) and are free to choose the optimal rate of food waste. The positive rate of food loss and waste follows from economic costs associated with the efforts to curb food loss and waste. In this section, we introduce a function representing the cost associated with food loss and waste abatement and investigate its properties. The same functional form will later be used at each stage of the supply chain, with different values of its exogenous parameters. The abatement cost function is the way we endogenize the rate of edible food waste in our model. Examples of food waste abatement activities include more frequent visits to a grocery store or more careful peeling of potatoes.

Denote the rate of edible food waste as $0 < \alpha_A \leq 1$ and the rate of inedible food waste as $0 \leq \bar{\alpha}_U \leq 1$. The rate of food available for sale (consumption) is then $\delta = 1 - \bar{\alpha}_U - \alpha_A$. Denote the production (purchases) of food before accounting for waste as Q and the corresponding quantity adjusted for waste (i.e., sales or consumption) as X , where $Q = X / (1 - \bar{\alpha}_U - \alpha_A)$. The proposed food waste abatement cost function takes the form

$$\tilde{C} = E \underbrace{\left(\frac{X}{\delta} \right)^\tau}_{\text{scale effect}} \underbrace{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta \bar{\alpha}_U}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_U} \right)}_{\text{food waste rate effect}} = E \frac{(1 - \bar{\alpha}_U - \alpha_A)^\tau}{X^\tau} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta \bar{\alpha}_U}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_U} \right), \quad [1]$$

where $E > 0$ is a calibrating constant, and τ and θ are shape parameters. The parameter θ represents the importance of the rate of inedible food waste for the marginal food waste abatement cost with respect to the rate of edible food waste. As shown in equation [1], the food loss and waste abatement cost function has two components. The first one relates to the quantity of food produced (purchased). We call it the scale effect to stress that agents in the food supply chain can adjust the scale of their production (purchases) as one of the options to reduce their food loss and waste abatement cost. The other option is to adjust the rate of edible food loss or waste.

In the absence of sufficient data to econometrically estimate these two parameters, we calibrate τ based on observed data and choose θ in line with prior requirements in the abatement

cost function. One of them is that the abatement cost be non-negative, which requires that $1 - \bar{\alpha}_U (1 + \theta \alpha_A) \geq 0$.

To look into the interpretation of parameter τ , let us calculate the scale elasticity of the abatement cost function in [1], that is, $\frac{\partial \tilde{C}}{\partial X} \frac{X}{\tilde{C}} = -\tau$. Therefore, τ is the negative of the scale elasticity of the food waste abatement cost function of an economic actor.

We can use the specification on the right of [1] to check the values it takes in two extreme situations for the rate of edible food waste —i) the rate is as high as possible (i.e., $\alpha_A = 1 - \bar{\alpha}_U$), in which case the abatement cost is zero,¹ and ii) the rate approaches zero (i.e., $\alpha_A \rightarrow 0^+$), in which case the abatement cost becomes extremely high (i.e., $\tilde{C} \rightarrow \infty$). The behavior of the food loss and waste abatement cost function in the two specific cases is in line with what one would expect.

Now, we discuss two assumptions one could make about the abatement cost function and investigate which parameter values are consistent with them. The first assumption is that, other things held constant, the abatement cost increases when the rate of edible food waste decreases (i.e., $\partial \tilde{C} / \partial \alpha_A < 0$). This is because an agent needs to use more effort to reduce the (already low) existing rate of edible food waste. Although the results for the behavior of the abatement cost function in the two extreme cases in the previous paragraph suggest this assumption always holds, it is possible that the abatement cost function is not monotonic in α_A throughout its domain. It can be shown that $\partial \tilde{C} / \partial \alpha_A < 0$ occurs as long as

$$\tau \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta \bar{\alpha}_U}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_U} \right) + \frac{\delta}{\alpha_A^2} > 0. \quad [2]$$

Second, a decrease in the rate of inedible food waste, other things held constant, reduces abatement cost (i.e., $\partial \tilde{C} / \partial \bar{\alpha}_U > 0$) because the decrease creates more room for edible food waste reduction (i.e., the term $1 - \bar{\alpha}_U$ grows). This occurs as long as

$$\tau \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_A} - \frac{\theta \bar{\alpha}_U}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_U} \right) + \frac{\theta \delta}{(1 - \bar{\alpha}_U)^2} < 0. \quad [3]$$

The first and second assumption are satisfied simultaneously when

¹ For completeness, we point out a special case in which our abatement function is not defined: $\alpha_A = 1 - \bar{\alpha}_U$ and at the same time, $\tau = 0$.

$$\frac{\theta}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_U)^2} - \frac{1}{\alpha_A^2} < 0. \quad [4]$$

While inequality [4] can be satisfied for some positive value of θ , it is always satisfied when $\theta < 0$. Moreover, $\theta < 0$ implies that the earlier condition, $1 - \bar{\alpha}_U (1 + \theta\alpha_A) \geq 0$, is satisfied as well. These two reasons motivate our choice of the parameter value in the empirical model.

Now that we have determined the necessary sign of parameter θ , we can go one step further and determine the minimum (from inequality [2]) and the maximum (from inequality [3]) value of parameter τ , for which both earlier assumptions are met

$$\tau_{\min} = -\frac{\delta(1-\bar{\alpha}_U)}{\alpha_A [1-\bar{\alpha}_U (1+\theta\alpha_A)]}$$

and

$$\tau_{\max} = -\frac{\theta\delta\alpha_A}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_U)[1-\bar{\alpha}_U (1+\theta\alpha_A)]}.$$

For illustration, suppose that $\alpha_A = 0.20$, $\bar{\alpha}_U = 0.10$, and $\theta = -1$. Then $\tau_{\min} = -3.42$ and $\tau_{\max} = 0.17$. The empirical boundary values change, depending on the values of α_A , $\bar{\alpha}_U$, and θ and give information on where the scale parameter τ can lie such that the food loss and waste abatement cost function possesses the required properties.

Finally, we will analyze under what conditions the concept of economies of scale, that is, that greater production reduces unit cost applies to our specification of the abatement cost function. In short, we want to know for which values of parameter τ $\partial AC/\partial Q < 0$ holds. Recalling that $AC = \tilde{C}/Q$ and $Q = X/(1-\bar{\alpha}_U - \alpha_A)$, equation [1] can be used to determine that $\partial AC/\partial Q < 0$ holds for $\tau > -1$.

Using four distinct values of τ , in Figure 5 we illustrate the behavior of the food waste abatement cost function. In each panel of Figure 5, we assume: $E = 1$, $\bar{\alpha}_U = 0.2$, and $\theta = -1$. The abatement cost increases as expected in every figure when α_A approaches 0. This indicates that complete abatement of food waste becomes very costly. The effect of τ is different. Figure 6A shows the abatement costs with $\tau = 1.5$ (this value implies economies of scale for our abatement cost function). An increase in food purchases when purchases are low sharply decreases the abatement cost; this effect flattens out as purchases become larger.

Figure 5B shows the abatement costs for $\tau = -1.5$ (no economies of scale). It shows sharply increasing abatement costs when Q increases. Furthermore, the figure shows that the cost does not increase monotonically as α decreases.

Figure 5C is qualitatively similar to figure 5A, however the scale effect is less pronounced, that is, an increase in Q does not decrease the abatement cost as fast as in figure 5A. Finally, figure 5D shows a case of economies to scale as $\tau = -0.5 > -1$, although the level of food waste abatement cost increases in Q . Which of the four distinct cases occurs, depends on the producer's (consumer's) behavior with respect to the selected commodity.

Figure 5: Food waste abatement cost function for different values of τ

4. Modeling structure

The food supply chain model that we use to simulate the economic effects of food loss and waste reduction along the supply chain, consists of six linked modules. First, we present the module for the farmer (subscript F) that includes both pre- and post-harvest losses. Then, we present modules for transport, handling, and storage (THS) (subscript T); the processor (subscript P); the retail sector (subscript R), and the hotel, restaurant, and institutions (HRI) sector (subscript H). At the end of the supply chain is the consumer. The consumer can choose to eat food at home (subscript C) or away from home in the HRI sector (subscript A). Finally, we present how individual modules are linked.

4.1. Farmer

Farmer's module is the most complex part of our model. It is because, on the one hand, it distinguishes between pre-harvest and post-harvest losses and, on the other hand, considers uncertainty, a key feature of agricultural production that has implications for other parts of the supply chain.² To keep the presentation of the module tractable, we proceed in steps. We start with the distinction between potential and actual yield. The term potential yield is a multifaceted concept. To simplify our analysis, we assume it consists of only two components: i) the choice of efforts to abate pre-harvest losses for a given plant cultivar, and ii) the choice of a plant cultivar for a given amount of abatement efforts.³

Farmers typically have several options if they want to reduce pre-harvest losses. Suppose the farmer produces potatoes and uses two options to mitigate pre-harvest losses (e.g., spraying and irrigation). Denote their quantities as x_1 (liters of pesticides) and x_2 (liters of water). The corresponding per unit costs of the two efforts are z_1 and z_2 , yielding the total cost of $z_1x_1 + z_2x_2$ for their use. These efforts can complement each other but likely partially substitute each other. To capture this, let X denote the aggregate farmer's effort in preventing pre-harvest losses; we model it as a CES (constant elasticity of substitution) aggregator

² Each stage in the supply chain faces uncertainty; however, it is arguably most pronounced at the producer level. To keep the model tractable, we only model uncertainty there.

³ This approach also applies to meat or fish production as long as it is produced in a farming system. In case of wild fish, the pre-harvest part of the farmer (producer) module would have to be deactivated as there is arguably not much a producer can do to reduce pre-harvest losses.

$$X = F \left[\omega x_1^\mu + (1-\omega)x_2^\mu \right]^\nu, \quad [5]$$

where F is effort productivity, ω is a share parameter, ν denotes the degree of homogeneity of the aggregator function, and $\sigma = 1/(1-\mu)$ is the substitution elasticity between x_1 and x_2 , which can be varied in simulations to reflect different substitution possibilities between x_1 and x_2 .

Let $G(X) \in [0,1)$ represent a function that translates the aggregate effort of the farmer into the share of preserved potential yield. We assume $G_x > 0$ and $G_{xx} < 0$. There are many functions that satisfy the three conditions above. In the empirical part of our model, we will use the exponential functional form of $G(X)$. Our choice is motivated by the minimal (one) parameter requirement of this function, which makes it attractive in the calibration stage of the empirical model. To summarize the above, if the maximum yield (say in controlled conditions) of a cultivar is y , then the yield the farmer achieves is $G(X)y < y$.

Now, we discuss the second part of the potential yield: choice of a cultivar for a given set of efforts to abate the pre-harvest losses. Choosing a cultivar is a strategy to reduce pre-harvest losses. We assume there is a continuum of cultivars, each of them characterized by a maximum yield y achievable under controlled conditions. Denote \bar{y} as the yield of the highest-yielding cultivar among all cultivars; this would be the highest theoretically achievable yield under controlled conditions. Denote $c(y)$ as the cost per hectare for the farmer of purchasing a cultivar with maximum yield y from the seed provider. We assume $c_y > 0$ and $c_{yy} > 0$.

The farmer faces pre-harvest losses that are affected by uncertainties and his efforts to reduce these losses and post-harvest losses that occur after the uncertainty has been resolved. The farmer operates under two sources of uncertainty: weather and output price. The weather can be bad (B) with probability ψ or good (G) with probability $1-\psi$. Likewise, the output price can be low (L) with probability φ or high (H) with probability $1-\varphi$. Table 3 presents the joint probabilities associated with the four states of nature. The uncertainty due to weather is independent of what happens to market prices; the converse is not necessarily true, however, as prices might be affected by weather. While we recognize this possibility, we assume the farmer faces an output price that is determined on a large enough market that is not affected by the local weather conditions the farmer faces. We assume both uncertainties are resolved just before harvest, and there is no uncertainty thereafter.

Table 3: States of nature and their probabilities

	Low price	High price
Bad weather	$\psi\varphi$	$\psi(1-\varphi)$
Good weather	$(1-\psi)\varphi$	$(1-\psi)(1-\varphi)$

The representative farmer is a risk-avertter with a strictly concave Bernoulli utility function $u(\pi)$. The farmer maximizes the expected von Neumann-Morgenstern utility (EU) by choosing a vector of variables consisting of yield y (a proxy for cultivar), amounts of efforts x_1 and x_2 to abate pre-harvest losses and state-specific harvest areas ($a_{FH}^{B,L}, a_{FH}^{B,H}, a_{FH}^{G,L}, a_{FH}^{G,H}$) and state-specific post-harvest rates of edible food loss ($\alpha_F^{B,L}, \alpha_F^{B,H}, \alpha_F^{G,L}, \alpha_F^{G,H}$). The choice variables y , x_1 , and x_2 do not carry any superscript because the farmer needs to decide on them before the state of nature has been revealed. The farmer's problem can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max EU &= \psi\varphi u(\pi_F^{B,L}) + \psi(1-\varphi)u(\pi_F^{B,H}) + (1-\psi)\varphi u(\pi_F^{G,L}) + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi)u(\pi_F^{G,H}) \\
 s.t. & \\
 \pi_F^{B,L} &= P_F^L \delta_F^{B,L} (1-l^B) [a_{FH}^{B,L} G^B(X)y] - a_p [c_0 + c(y)] - z_1 x_1 - z_2 x_2 - \tilde{C}_F^B(a_{FH}^{B,L}) - \tilde{C}_F(\alpha_F^{B,L}, q_F^{B,L}) - (w_{\zeta_F^D}^D - s_{\zeta_F^U}^U) \frac{(1-\delta_F^{B,L})}{\delta_F^{B,L}} q_F^{B,L} \\
 \pi_F^{B,H} &= P_F^H \delta_F^{B,H} (1-l^B) [a_{FH}^{B,H} G^B(X)y] - a_p [c_0 + c(y)] - z_1 x_1 - z_2 x_2 - \tilde{C}_F^B(a_{FH}^{B,H}) - \tilde{C}_F(\alpha_F^{B,H}, q_F^{B,H}) - (w_{\zeta_F^D}^D - s_{\zeta_F^U}^U) \frac{(1-\delta_F^{B,H})}{\delta_F^{B,H}} q_F^{B,H} \\
 \pi_F^{G,L} &= P_F^L \delta_F^{G,L} (1-l^G) [a_{FH}^{G,L} G^G(X)y] - a_p [c_0 + c(y)] - z_1 x_1 - z_2 x_2 - \tilde{C}_F^G(a_{FH}^{G,L}) - \tilde{C}_F(\alpha_F^{G,L}, q_F^{G,L}) - (w_{\zeta_F^D}^D - s_{\zeta_F^U}^U) \frac{(1-\delta_F^{G,L})}{\delta_F^{G,L}} q_F^{G,L} \\
 \pi_F^{G,H} &= P_F^H \delta_F^{G,H} (1-l^G) [a_{FH}^{G,H} G^G(X)y] - a_p [c_0 + c(y)] - z_1 x_1 - z_2 x_2 - \tilde{C}_F^G(a_{FH}^{G,H}) - \tilde{C}_F(\alpha_F^{G,H}, q_F^{G,H}) - (w_{\zeta_F^D}^D - s_{\zeta_F^U}^U) \frac{(1-\delta_F^{G,H})}{\delta_F^{G,H}} q_F^{G,H} \\
 q_F^{B,L} &= \delta_F^{B,L} (1-l^B) [a_{FH}^{B,L} G^B(X)y] \\
 q_F^{B,H} &= \delta_F^{B,H} (1-l^B) [a_{FH}^{B,H} G^B(X)y] \\
 q_F^{G,L} &= \delta_F^{G,L} (1-l^G) [a_{FH}^{G,L} G^G(X)y] \\
 q_F^{G,H} &= \delta_F^{G,H} (1-l^G) [a_{FH}^{G,H} G^G(X)y] \\
 a_{FH}^{B,L}, a_{FH}^{B,H}, a_{FH}^{G,L}, a_{FH}^{G,H} &\leq a_p
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where, the variables π_F and q_F (with appropriate superscripts) represent profits and the post-harvest production in individual states of nature.

The superscripts generally denote the state of nature. l^B denotes the share of pre-harvest production lost due to bad weather ($l^G = 0$), a_p is that planted area, c_0 is the cost per hectare related to planting the crop, other than the seed cost $c(y)$, $\tilde{C}(\cdot)$ is the harvest cost function ($\tilde{C}' > 0, \tilde{C}'' > 0$), $\tilde{C}(\cdot)$ is the post-harvest food loss abatement cost function, w is the cost of

disposition per unit of food waste, s is the price received for a unit of food waste delivered for upscaling, ξ_F^D and ξ_F^U denote exogenous shares of the total quantity of food waste going to dispositions and upcycling (U) ($\xi_F^D + \xi_F^U = 1$).

The corresponding eleven first-order conditions are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial y} &= \psi \varphi u'(\pi_F^{B,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial y} + \psi (1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{B,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial y} + (1-\psi) \varphi u'(\pi_F^{G,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial y} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{G,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial y} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial x_1} &= \psi \varphi u'(\pi_F^{B,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial x_1} + \psi (1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{B,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial x_1} + (1-\psi) \varphi u'(\pi_F^{G,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial x_1} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{G,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial x_1} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial x_2} &= \psi \varphi u'(\pi_F^{B,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial x_2} + \psi (1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{B,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial x_2} + (1-\psi) \varphi u'(\pi_F^{G,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial x_2} + (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{G,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial x_2} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,L}} &= \psi \varphi u'(\pi_F^{B,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,L}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,H}} &= \psi (1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{B,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,H}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,L}} &= (1-\psi) \varphi u'(\pi_F^{G,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,L}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,H}} &= (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{G,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,H}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,L}} &= \psi \varphi u'(\pi_F^{B,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,L}}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,L}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,H}} &= \psi (1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{B,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{B,H}}{\partial \alpha_H^{B,H}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,L}} &= (1-\psi) \varphi u'(\pi_F^{G,L}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,L}}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,L}} = 0 \\
 \frac{\partial EU}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,H}} &= (1-\psi)(1-\varphi) u'(\pi_F^{G,H}) \frac{\partial \pi_F^{G,H}}{\partial \alpha_H^{G,H}} = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

4.2. Transport, handling, and storage

The THS sector is modeled⁴ to buy a quantity of product (e.g., potatoes) q_S^T from the farmer at a price P_F (i.e., the sales price of the farmer equals the purchase price of THS) and process it (e.g., transporting or cooling), incurring production cost $C_T(\cdot)$, to sell the resulting quantity q_T (net of food waste) at a price P_T to the next stage in the supply chain (processor): $q_T = \delta_T B_T q_S^T$, where B_T is the transformation coefficient that captures shrinkage. \tilde{C}_T is the food waste abatement cost

⁴ Many processing companies will buy directly from the farmer and have the logistics handled by a third-party (THS). Our modelling approach allows for this possibility as the product needs to pass physically through THS, and part of it will be wasted. Moreover, the third-part company makes profits in reality, which is captured by the profit-maximizing behavior we model in [8].

function of the THS sector; other parameters have a similar meaning as explained earlier for the farmer's module. The THS profit maximization problem is

$$\begin{aligned} \max \pi_T &= P_T q_T - P_F q_S^T - C_T(q_T) - \tilde{C}_T(\alpha_T, q_T) - (w_{\zeta_T}^{\zeta^D} - s_{\zeta_T}^{\zeta^U})(1 - \delta_T) B_T q_S^T \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ q_T &= \delta_T B_T q_S^T \end{aligned} \quad [8]$$

Substituting q_S^T from the constraint into the objective function and taking the first-order conditions, with respect to q_T and α_T we obtain:

$$q_T : P_T - \frac{P_F}{\delta_T B_T} - C_T' - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_T}{\partial q_T} - \frac{(w_{\zeta_T}^{\zeta^D} - s_{\zeta_T}^{\zeta^U})(1 - \delta_T)}{\delta_T} = 0 \quad [9]$$

$$\alpha_T : -\frac{P_T q_T}{B_T \delta_T^2} - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_T}{\partial \alpha_T} - (w_{\zeta_T}^{\zeta^D} - s_{\zeta_T}^{\zeta^U}) \frac{q_T}{\delta_T^2} = 0 \quad [10]$$

4.3. Processor

The processor buys input q_S^P (potatoes) from the THS sector and produces output (e.g., frozen French fries) denoted by q_P which is later sold to the retailer and food services (HRI) at a price P_P . Because the structure of the processor's module is identical to the problem of the THS sector, we do not present the notation in detail.

$$\begin{aligned} \max \pi_P &= P_P q_P - P_T q_S^P - C_P(q_P) - \tilde{C}_P(\alpha_P, q_P) - (w_{\zeta_P}^{\zeta^D} - s_{\zeta_P}^{\zeta^U})(1 - \delta_P) B_P q_S^P \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ q_P &= \delta_P B_P q_S^P \end{aligned} \quad [11]$$

Substituting q_S^P from the constraint into the objective function and taking the first-order conditions, with respect to q_P and α_P we obtain:

$$q_P : P_P - \frac{P_T}{\delta_P B_P} - C_P' - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_P}{\partial q_P} - \frac{(w_{\zeta_P}^{\zeta^D} - s_{\zeta_P}^{\zeta^U})(1 - \delta_P)}{\delta_P} = 0 \quad [12]$$

$$\alpha_P : -\frac{P_T q_P}{B_P \delta_P^2} - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_P}{\partial \alpha_P} - (w_{\zeta_P}^{\zeta^D} - s_{\zeta_P}^{\zeta^U}) \frac{q_P}{\delta_P^2} = 0 \quad [13]$$

4.4. Retail

The retail sector is the next element of our supply chain. The retailer purchases input (e.g., frozen French fries) from the processor and sells it directly to the consumer (for consumption at home). The formulation of the retailer's problem does not differ from the THS or processor's specification

$$\begin{aligned} \max \pi_R &= P_R q_R - P_P q_S^R - C_R(q_R) - \tilde{C}_R(\alpha_R, q_R) - (w_{\zeta_R^D} - s_{\zeta_R^U})(1 - \delta_R) B_R q_S^R \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ q_R &= \delta_R B_R q_S^R \end{aligned} \quad [14]$$

with corresponding first-order conditions

$$q_R : P_R - \frac{P_P}{\delta_R B_R} - C_R' - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_R}{\partial q_R} - \frac{(w_{\zeta_R^D} - s_{\zeta_R^U})(1 - \delta_R)}{\delta_R} = 0 \quad [15]$$

$$\alpha_R : -\frac{P_P q_R}{B_R \delta_R^2} - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_R}{\partial \alpha_R} - (w_{\zeta_R^D} - s_{\zeta_R^U}) \frac{q_R}{\delta_R^2} = 0 \quad [16]$$

4.5. Hotels, restaurants, and institutions

The HRI sector purchases inputs q_S^H (e.g., frozen French fries) from the processor.⁵ During the preparation of meals to be eaten away from home, a portion is wasted (edible and inedible) such that the quantity of food that makes it to the consumer's plate in a restaurant is $q_H = \delta_H B_H q_S^H$, where, B_H denotes a transformation coefficient. The price of food away from home is P_H .

In addition to the waste associated with food preparation, there is also the waste of consumers produced while eating food away from home. We denote the proportion of the edible waste by α_A . We treat this share as exogenous to consumers but allow the HRI sector to choose it optimally, as the HRI is responsible for disposing of the waste generated by consumers. Actions to reduce this waste include serving smaller portions, reducing the offer of buffet meals, or hiring a better chef. We denote the abatement cost of these options as $\hat{C}_H(\cdot)$.

The HRI profit maximization problem can be written as

⁵ In some empirical instances it might be more common that HRI buy from wholesalers rather than directly from processors. We do not model the wholesale sector, as this would be just an extra stage in the supply chain between the processor and the HRI without any qualitative implications for the results.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max \pi_H &= P_H q_H - P_P q_S^H - C_H(q_H) - \tilde{C}_H(\alpha_H, q_H) - \hat{C}_H(\alpha_A, q_A) - (w_{\zeta_H}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_H}^{zU})(1 - \delta_H) B_H q_S^H \\
 &- (w_{\zeta_A}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_A}^{zU})(1 - \delta_A) q_H \\
 \text{s.t.} & \\
 q_H &= \delta_H B_H q_S^H \\
 q_A &= \delta_A q_H
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

with the corresponding first-order conditions

$$q_H : P_H - \frac{P_P}{\delta_H B_H} - C_H' - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_H}{\partial q_H} - \frac{\partial \hat{C}_H}{\partial q_A} \delta_A - (w_{\zeta_H}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_H}^{zU}) \left(\frac{1}{\delta_H} - 1 \right) - (w_{\zeta_A}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_A}^{zU})(1 - \delta_A) = 0 \tag{18}$$

$$\alpha_H : -\frac{P_P q_H}{\delta_H^2 B_H} - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_H}{\partial \alpha_H} - (w_{\zeta_H}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_H}^{zU}) \frac{q_H}{\delta_H^2} = 0 \tag{19}$$

$$\alpha_A : -\frac{\partial \hat{C}_H}{\partial \alpha_A} + \frac{\partial \hat{C}_H}{\partial q_A} q_H - (w_{\zeta_A}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_A}^{zU}) q_H = 0. \tag{20}$$

4.6. Consumer

The consumer is the last segment of the food supply chain. She maximizes her utility u from consuming food (e.g., frozen French fries) at home (q_C), away from home (q_A), and the numeraire good N (i.e., the good the price of which is used as a means of comparison for other goods in the demand system) subject to the budget constraint (income is I) and a set of transformation conditions. Denote q_U as the quantity of purchased food from retail and D as the amount of food received from food banks (part of the FLW along the supply chain is collected and delivered to food banks at the consumer stage). Not all food from food banks can be entirely used; therefore, $0 < \rho \leq 1$ is a coefficient that indicates to what extent the donations are truly additional. Given the above, food consumption at home can be written as $q_C = \delta_C (q_U + \rho D)$.

The consumer utility maximization problem can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max u(q_C, q_A, N) &= \phi_C q_C + \phi_A q_A - \frac{1}{2} (\lambda_C q_C^2 + \lambda_A q_A^2 + 2\kappa q_C q_A) + N \\
 \text{s.t.} & \\
 P_U q_U + P_H q_H + N + \tilde{C}_C(\alpha_C, q_C) + (w_{\zeta_C}^{zD} - s_{\zeta_C}^{zU})(1 - \delta_C)(q_U + \rho D) &= I \\
 q_C &= \delta_C (q_U + \rho D) \\
 q_A &= \delta_A q_H \\
 \delta_C &= 1 - \bar{\alpha}_C - \alpha_C \\
 \delta_A &= 1 - \bar{\alpha}_A - \alpha_A
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where ϕ_C and ϕ_A determine the intrinsic value of food at home and away from home for the consumer, while λ_C and λ_A determine how fast marginal utility decreases when food intake increases. κ denotes the degree of substitutability between eating at home and away from home. When $\kappa = -1$ eating at home and away from home would be perfect complements, while $\kappa = 1$ means that they are perfect substitutes (Choi and Coughlan, 2006). P_U and P_H are the price of food purchases in retail and HRI, respectively. \tilde{C}_C is consumer's food waste abatement cost function at home.

Expressing N from the budget constraint and substituting it along with other constraints into the objective function yields an unconstrained optimization problem with the corresponding first-order conditions

$$q_C : \phi_C - \lambda_C q_C - \kappa q_A - \frac{P_U}{\delta_C} - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_C}{\partial q_C} - (w_{\xi_C^D} - s_{\xi_C^U}) \left(\frac{1}{\delta_C} - 1 \right) = 0 \quad [22]$$

$$q_A : \phi_A - \lambda_A q_A - \kappa q_C - \frac{P_H}{\delta_A} = 0 \quad [23]$$

$$\alpha_C : - \left[P_U + (w_{\xi_C^D} - s_{\xi_C^U}) \right] \frac{q_C}{\delta_C^2} - \frac{\partial \tilde{C}_C}{\partial \alpha_C} = 0 \quad [24]$$

4.7. Market equilibrium

The optimal response of the farmer to the uncertainty she faces is a vector of alternative production plans $q_F^{B,L}$, $q_F^{B,H}$, $q_F^{G,L}$, and $q_F^{G,H}$ of which only one will be realized after the state of nature is known after harvest. To link the farmer's module with the rest of the model, we define post-harvest quantity sold to the transportation, handling, and storage sector as follows

$$q_F = \gamma_{B,L} q_F^{B,L} + \gamma_{B,H} q_F^{B,H} + \gamma_{G,L} q_F^{G,L} + \gamma_{G,H} q_F^{G,H},$$

where $\gamma_{B,L} + \gamma_{B,H} + \gamma_{G,L} + \gamma_{G,H} = 1$, and $\gamma_i = \{0,1\}$ for $i = \{(B,L), (B,H), (G,L), (G,H)\}$. The parameter γ_i is a binomial weight parameter randomly chosen with a probability corresponding to the state of nature.

Likewise, we model the expectation (in the farm module) and the actual realization (in the transportation, handling, and storage module) of the price received by the farmer. Two situations are possible: either $P_F^H = P_F$ and $P_F^L = (1 - \vartheta_L) P_F$ or $P_F^L = P_F$ and $P_F^H = (1 + \vartheta_H) P_F$, where ϑ_H and ϑ_L

denote the (exogenous) percentage differences of the high and low price, respectively, relative to the observe market price P_F after the state of nature has been revealed.

The market equilibrium consists of the 23 first-order conditions identified above and the following 13 conditions.

The amount of food purchased by the THS sector equals the sum of what the farmer sells and the net trade $NT_F(P_F)$ (exports minus imports) of food at farm level

$$q_S^T = q_F - NT_F(P_F). \quad [25]$$

Here P_F denotes the price actually received by the farmer after the uncertainty about the weather and price has been revealed.

The amount of food purchased by the processor equals the sum of what the THS sector sells and the net trade of food at THS level

$$q_S^P = q_T - NT_T(P_T). \quad [26]$$

The total amount of food purchased by retailers and HRI equals the sum of what the processor sells and the net trade in processed food. The following equation provides the split of the food generated by the processor between the retailer and HRI

$$q_S^R + q_S^H = q_P - NT_P(P_P). \quad [27]$$

Retailer's sales are equal to consumer's purchases for home consumption

$$q_R = q_U. \quad [28]$$

Equations [29] to [34] link the maximum production/consumption at a given stage of the supply chain to the final production/consumption by taking food loss and waste into account

$$q_T = \delta_T B_T q_S^T \quad [29]$$

$$q_P = \delta_P B_P q_S^P \quad [30]$$

$$q_R = \delta_R B_R q_S^R \quad [31]$$

$$q_H = \delta_H B_H q_S^H \quad [32]$$

$$q_A = \delta_A q_H \quad [33]$$

$$q_C = \delta_C (q_U + \rho D). \quad [34]$$

Equation [35] equates food donations consumed by the consumer (D) to the sum of donations provided by the rest of the supply chain, which we represent by a supply curve of donations denoted by $S_D(w)$

$$D = S_D(w) . \quad [35]$$

The sell price of the retailer equals the purchase price of the consumer

$$P_R = P_U . \quad [36]$$

The sum of all the dispositions has to be equal to the sum of all food wasted in the supply chain

$$R(w) + S_D(w) + L(w) = \xi_F^D \frac{(1-\delta_F)}{\delta_F} q_F + \xi_T^D (1-\delta_T) B_T q_S^T + \xi_P^D (1-\delta_P) B_P q_S^P + \xi_R^D (1-\delta_R) B_R q_S^R + \xi_H^D (1-\delta_H) B_H q_S^H + \xi_A^D (1-\delta_A) q_H + \xi_C^D (1-\delta_C) (q_U + \rho D) \quad [37]$$

$R(\cdot)$, $S_D(\cdot)$, and $L(\cdot)$ represent marginal cost curves related to accommodating food waste in recycling, donations, and landfill (incineration), respectively. The price paid for food waste by the upcycling industry (s) is assumed to be exogenous.

The market equilibrium is found by solving 36 (= 23+13) equations for the following 36 unknowns

$$y, x_1, x_2, a_{FH}^{B,L}, a_{FH}^{B,H}, a_{FH}^{G,L}, a_{FH}^{G,L}, \alpha_{FH}^{B,L}, \alpha_{FH}^{B,H}, \alpha_{FH}^{G,L}, \alpha_{FH}^{G,L}, \alpha_T, \alpha_P, \alpha_R, \alpha_H, \alpha_A, \alpha_C, q_S^T, q_S^P, q_S^R, q_S^H, q_T, q_P, q_R, q_H, q_U, q_C, q_A, D, P_F, P_T, P_P, P_R, P_H, P_U, w$$

5. Modeling food loss and waste-reducing innovations

This chapter explains how the model could simulate the economic effects of the SILLs and the policy interventions that the Joint Research Center (JRC) proposed to reduce FLW. Each parameter that will be shocked to simulate a SILL or a policy has a different effect on the outcomes of the model.

SILL 1, 'Food loss and waste monitoring & assessment', aims to (i) deliver and pilot an open IT-based solution for capturing FLW data throughout the supply chain and providing analytics to address the requirements of the SDG Indicator 12.3.1 (Global Food Loss and Waste), the Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 and the Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/2000 and (ii) demonstrate the FLW monitoring & assessment solution in two EU countries, including Estonia, to ensure its applicability and replicability in different business and cultural settings (Cruijssen et al., 2022). This SILL focuses on ex-post measurement of the quantity of food waste. This does not directly affect an agent's internal drivers to reduce food waste. Therefore, our model is not in the position to model such an intervention.

The objective of SILL 2, 'Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food', is to (i) demonstrate the use of a combined intelligent-functional-sustainable packaging solution, combining biobased & biodegradable materials, packaging design and freshness indicators (intelligent label) to significantly reduce food waste and unsustainable packaging at the retail and consumer levels and (ii) demonstrate the use of software for reading freshness color changes of the intelligent packaging and transforming them into remaining shelf life, to allow retailers better manage their stock and reduce food waste (Cruijssen et al., 2022). Smart packaging takes away the uncertainty of whether the food is still safe to eat for consumers and retailers. It reduces 'better safe than sorry' behavior and thus reduces costs for post-packaging supply chain actors to avoid food waste. This intervention will, therefore, be modeled by lowering E_r and E_c which will lower the abatement costs for the retail sector and the consumer. The third SILL, 'Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre-)harvesting aligned with short-term demand', will demonstrate innovations for food loss reduction at the pre-harvest and harvest stages of fruit & vegetable greenhouse farms through (i) novel remote sensing solutions enabling accurate crop monitoring, fruit ripeness and yield estimation; (ii) automated produce quality evaluation and estimation of 'sub-standard' produce at the pre-harvest and harvest stages; (iii) data-driven optimization of combined harvest

scheduling and short-term predicted downstream demand (Cruijssen et al., 2022). The effect of this SILL is twofold. First, the SILL reduces pre-harvest losses through a pre-harvest loss abatement effort x . We will shock this variable to show the effects of the SILL on the producer level and the cascading effects on the other stages of the supply chain. Second, the SILL will reduce the probability of negative price shocks, as it better connects supply with demand through harvest scheduling. This is modeled by increasing the probability ψ of the farmer's module in the supply chain model.

SILL 4, 'Mobile food valorization as a service', will demonstrate (i) innovative, flexible, and versatile solutions as a service for optimizing the use of edible biomass (fresh produce and edible fractions); (ii) the economic viability of the business model applied and how the revenues will be distributed throughout the new value chains (Cruijssen et al., 2022). This SILL upscales the FLW of the original product and creates a new product. In our model, we do not simulate the supply chain of the upscaled product directly. However, we can show the impact of the FLW upcycling on the FLW production of the original product. The FLW upcycling is modeled by changing the price the upscaling sector is willing to pay for food waste and by increasing the exogenous share of food waste destined for the upscaling sector.

The fifth SILL, 'Ugly food identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorization', will (i) assess the shelf life and compliance of products to retail requirements (e.g., shape, size, ripeness, defects) at an early stage by non-destructive analysis and multi-attribute classification techniques, applied to a single fruit/vegetable or a whole lot/batch; (ii) to use the shelf-life and compliance assessment to reduce FLW at the producer and the retailer side; (iii) to ensure quality products with a known shelf-life at the retailer side, providing market strategies for ugly food and optimize logistics/storage management (Cruijssen et al., 2022). This SILL has two effects in the model: one effect at the producer stage and one at the retailer stage. For the producer, this SILL will reduce the disposition costs as it provides market strategies for ugly foods. Comparable to SILL 4, there will be a separate supply chain for the ugly foods. An exogenous share ξ of the food loss, which should be equal to the demand for the ugly food, will be marketed for a lower cost than the costs of disposition. Furthermore, this SILL will lower the abatement cost in the model of the retailer. The retailer can put less effort into assessing whether the product can still be sold.

The objective of the sixth SILL, 'Reduction through advanced data-driven production process control and optimization' is (i) to significantly reduce food loss in breaded poultry

production (most complex line in the factory, with reference products, cordon bleu, 'Flamenquin') through continuous advanced control & optimization of the key variables and impacting processes involved, for intermediates and the final product; (ii) to migrate from a human-based, low-automation and reactive, to a data-driven, fully controlled, proactive and optimized system; (iii) to integrate the developed solution in the current Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system of ALDELIS avoiding information silos (Crujssen et al., 2022). This SILL focuses on the processor stage of the chicken supply chain. The SILL will lower the food waste abatement costs through an improved and automatized production process. Therefore, it will be modeled by lowering the abatement cost function in the model for the processor stage of the chicken supply chain.

SILL 7, 'Food loss and waste reduction through efficient food bank networks', aims (i) to demonstrate innovative solutions that strengthen the role of foodbanks as food waste reduction players; (ii) to help European food banks to professionalize their operations, and as such to reduce food losses throughout the food chains, while at the same time helping more people that are hungry in Europe; (iii) to make foodbank-centered food chains not only more efficient but at the same time also more just; (iv) to ensure that the conflicts between FLW reduction & food poverty, are adequately addressed (Crujssen et al., 2022). When food banks become more efficient because of this SILL, more food will be donated by the supply chain actors. We model this by shocking the supply function of donations to the right.

The eighth SILL, 'retail food waste valorization through algae production for high-value applications', aims (i) to develop an optimal and feasible solution to in-store and in-warehouse FLW pre-treatment (especially fruits & vegetables & animal proteins), addressing waste from stores (and equivalent premises); (ii) to characterize the pre-treated FLW and valorize it into the production of micro-algae; (iii) to develop a reverse logistics processes that take into account safety regulations, business constraints, the complexity of FLW being decentralized in the retail context, and the use of an innovative hermetic container for transportation (Crujssen et al., 2022). This SILL will be modeled comparable to SILL 4 and 5. The retail sector can relocate a fixed share ξ_R that equals the demand for the algae products to the algae producer against lower costs than the costs of disposition. This will reduce the quantity of food waste in landfills and other destinations of FLW dispositions.

The last SILL (9), 'Fork to farm to fork: informing and nudging consumers to make better dietary choices' will (i) develop recipes with low FLW, high nutritional score, and low environmental impact; (ii) develop a food label and scores for FLW, nutritional value, and environmental impact, to trigger consumer behavioral change; (iii) demonstrate the use of macro-scale optimization models that balance FLW reduction with high nutritional value and food affordability (Crujssen et al., 2022). The recipes and labels with scores will lower the costs for consumers to reduce food waste. This is modeled through a reduction in the food waste abatement cost function for consumers.

6. Conclusions

We have presented a theoretical partial equilibrium model for a food supply chain that can be used to analyze the economic and environmental effects of diverse policy interventions and technological solutions to curb food loss and waste along a supply chain for a selected food commodity. We will use the presented theoretical framework in an empirical analysis to be performed in deliverable 1.3. Our model is an alternative to large, economy-wide economic computable general equilibrium models that are not able to capture specificities of commodity-level supply chains.

7. References

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